

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSES OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH PARAMETERS BETWEEN RUSSIA AND AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the economies of Russia and Azerbaijan due to their shared economic trajectory as post-Soviet countries with similar key economic resources. The countries share geographical similarities but differ in their physical, human, and natural resources. Since the collapse of the USSR, both nations have adopted a free-market system and continue to implement economic policies aimed at achieving growth and ensuring an equitable distribution of resources. The research aims to determine the extent to which the economic growth parameters of independent Russia and Azerbaijan from 2010 to 2020 show a shared long-run equilibrium and growth pattern. The methodology involves a time-series cross-sectional data analysis, comparing various economic parameters, including a single indicator like real GDP and normal income, as well as multidimensional indicators like the Human Development Index (HDI). The research concludes that there is a parallel long-run equilibrium relationship between Azerbaijan and Russia, primarily due to their shared economic structure and institutionalization. However, there are obvious variances between the two countries, as Russia faces specific external political influences and pressures that differ from Azerbaijan, which impacts the extent of their convergence.

Keywords: economic indicators, economic parameters, gini coefficient, inclusive growth.

Introduction

Russia and Azerbaijan share many commonalities, so it's expected that they would have linked economic structures, policies, and approaches to institutionalization. Until 1992, Azerbaijan was a state within the larger USSR, and most of its government structures and institutions were directly inherited from the Soviet system.

With the collapse of the USSR, most Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries, including Russia and Azerbaijan, were forced into a period of transition. This process pushed these states to not only provide public goods but also to allow for private sector development to create a competitive economic structure (Recepoglu, 2022). This required a systematic reduction in government spending and the implementation of new, sweeping economic regulations. The post-socialist transformation from a planned to a market economy did not happen uniformly for every country, as it involved major structural differences such as economic infrastructure, political systems, geographical location, institutional success, democratic culture, and natural resources (Gunes & Hajiyeva, 2020).

Attracting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) was a key economic driver for achieving a market-oriented economy. Both the Russian and Azerbaijani governments tried to implement policies that would support the inflow of FDI. In 1993, the Russian government passed a presidential decree to propose legislation facilitating the flow of foreign capital into oil extraction and development projects. Similarly, in 1994, the Azerbaijani government entered into the "Contract of the Century" with a consortium of oil companies and subsequently adopted the law on the protection of foreign investments in 1995 (Bayulgen, 2014). These strategic economic accomplishments led to an increase in FDI, and consequently, both countries experienced significant growth. In the decade following the "Contract of the Century," Azerbaijan's GDP increased more than

14-fold. This brought about an increase in GDP per capita, which rose from about \$3,534 in 2000 to \$17,782 in 2015. As the government budget grew, government expenditure also increased in critical sectors, causing the economy to expand (Falkowski, 2018).

Russia's economy has experienced different cycles and fluctuations, particularly in the transition from the pre-USSR era (Mazat & Serrano, 1993) to the post-USSR era, despite having benefited tremendously from the union. This was because economic activities were centralized and coordinated through Moscow. Another significant shift in the Russian economy was the impact of the Cold War, which led to the end of the Soviet Union. The tightening of global economic activity, which prevented Russia's engagement in the world economy, significantly impacted its political system, structure, and ability to develop and grow its GDP. As the newly independent states moved further away from economic interdependency with Russia and integrated into the global economy, Russia was left in isolation. The Baltic republics, for example, signed an association agreement with the European Union, while other states formed different regional and global preferential trade agreements (Benešová & Smutka, 2016).

The justification for applying analysis to the inclusive economic growth parameters of Russia and Azerbaijan is based on the recognition that both countries share significant historical and structural economic similarities. Cointegration methods allow researchers to analyze long-term relationships among these non-stationary variables by treating them as if they were stationary, which allows for more robust and valid econometric conclusions.

Overall, the study demonstrates that there is a correlation between the economic growth approaches of Russia and Azerbaijan. However, this correlation can also be described as partial because the study also shows divergent levels and disparities in poverty and

inequality. The research reveals that a long-run equilibrium exists between economic growth and reduced income inequality. Additionally, there is a relationship between government policy and the creation of sustainable employment.

Literature Review

Since its independence, Azerbaijan has continued to move toward democratization and a free-market economy. Emerging from the Soviet system, the country, like all others in the post-Soviet period, was confronted by dysfunction, fundamental institutional change, rapid attitudinal and behavioral adjustments to an ever-changing structure of opportunities, anti-regime mass mobilization, ethnic violence, and the driving force of intense nationalism (Bonnell & Breslauer, 2009).

During this same period, according to financial institutions such as the IMF and the World Bank, Azerbaijan's economy has gone through multiple business cycle phases of economic growth. It experienced a sharp contraction in the early 1990s, when GDP fell by over 70%, followed by a period of stabilization that preceded the entrance of oil company conglomerates into the country. During this time, the average annual growth was about 20% per year, driven by oil revenue (International Monetary Fund, 1998). By 2006, experiencing a boom, real GDP growth reached about 31%. World Bank reports indicate that the predominant export of the Azerbaijani economy, oil and gas, jumped from roughly 50% to 90% (International Monetary Fund, 1998; The World Bank Group, 2022).

During the boom period, as a result of the increase in revenue from the exploration of oil and gas, the economy began to see possibilities for diversification and improvement in different sectors. Ideally, an increase in revenue comes from an increase in GDP and economic growth. However, there was also a negative effect of the oil boom, as it impacted the government's strategic institutionalization away from the Soviet system due to the massive accumulation of wealth. This was coupled with high inflation due to rapid growth. An aspect of the macroeconomic objective that was most impacted was the increased inequality in the country (The World Bank Group, 2022). Studies show that there is a positive relationship between financial development, economic growth, and income inequality and poverty (Ali et al., 2022).

Despite government efforts at diversification, the economy of Azerbaijan is primarily dependent on oil and gas. A large proportion of the economy's revenue is derived from oil, gas, and associated industries (The World Bank Group, 2022). Over the years, since experiencing an economic boom, the government has prioritized the development of this sector. It has invested heavily in transportation infrastructure for the easy delivery of oil and gas products to the world market, especially to European consumers.

The development of the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil pipeline and the subsequent development of the Trans-Caspian pipeline has brought about robust economic growth, but also the drawback of a deepening reliance on oil and gas (Sovacool, 2011). In 1999, the government of Azerbaijan established the State Oil Fund.

Over many years, through the expenditure of accumulated revenue, the State Oil Fund has been capable of supporting economic growth (Aliyev et al., 2017). The fund served as an effective stabilizer during periods of recession, particularly the financial crises of 2008 and 2013 (Aslanli, 2015). The IMF report for 2021 also stated that this was the case during the COVID-19 pandemic, whereby expenditure from the State Oil Fund was able to cushion the effect of the global recession on the Azerbaijani economic outlook (International Monetary Fund, 2021).

Right at the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia, which had been a dominantly planned and controlled economy, had to move to a market-based economy. One of the key driving policies was the privatization of government entities. This change in economic policies led to an economy dominated by oligarchs. The oligarchs owe their fortunes to the "loans-for-shares" auctions in which the government appointed commercial bankers to run the auction. This led to the allocation of massive control of natural resource enterprises (Guriev & Rachinsky, 2005). The scheme led to a concentration of wealth in the hands of a few; rather than creating an expansion of wealth and a reduction in inequality, it further dissipated the economy. Although there is evidence that the oligopolistic market structure that ensued did provide more employment opportunities for the population, as with this type of market structure, it also created massive market failure. The oligarch-owned firms are usually less efficient since they operate as a conglomerate, and therefore there exist multilayered agency problems and capital inefficiency compared to stand-alone firms (Guriev & Rachinsky, 2005).

Inclusive economic growth is multifaceted and goes beyond the contemporary understanding of a country's growth. Inclusive growth was born as a challenge to the general concept of economic growth, which increases inequality and does not cause positive changes in countries with a low level of development (Saher et al., 2024). Emphasizing the understanding from Junankar et al. (1992), Kakwani & Siddiqui (2023) stated that economic growth provides the means, but distribution is fundamental to economic and social equality and that "economic growth is very important as a means for bettering people's lives, but to go much faster, it has to be combined with devoting resources to remove illiteracy, ill health, undernutrition, and other deprivations."

In the article "The Concept of Inclusive Economic Growth," Walby (2018) argues for the need to repudiate the claim that there is a trade-off between growth and equality because it is used to block social-democratic agendas. Instead, growth should be viewed through the lens of social inclusion, which is necessary for economic growth (Walby, 2018).

According to Ngepah (2017), the concept of inclusive economic growth is relatively nascent. Contrary to the traditional concept of pro-poor growth, which more or less places those at the lower end of the income/wealth distribution spectrum at the margin of wealth creation processes, the concept of inclusive growth suggests a more active participation of the poor.

The definition of growth itself generally carries a connotation of quantitative increase; therefore, economic growth is essentially a qualitative concept, hence the measurement of factors of economic activities contributing to the achievement of higher states of human welfare (Shearer, 1961).

An inclusive economy, as defined by Saher et al. (2024), is one that creates a broader range of opportunities for shared prosperity, especially for people and organizations who face the most significant obstacles to improving their well-being. Early studies have shown the correlation between growth and inequality. Economic growth does not always achieve the desired outcome of reducing inequality; rather, as revealed by the Kuznets curve, it can induce political instability and autocratic disaster with high inequality and low output in production (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2002). Kuznets hypothesized that in the early stages of development, growth produces (and exploits) inequality, and as per capita income rises, there comes a turning point after which inequality declines because the first growth not only produces but, in fact, necessitates income inequality (Ranieri & Ramos, 2013).

Furthermore, according to the International Policy Centre for Inclusive Growth, the concept of inclusive growth can be understood in the context of an unfolding shift in development thinking away from seeing equity either as a toll on growth or as a byproduct of growth. Not only is growth with equity possible, but growth and poverty and inequality reduction can also be instrumental to each other (Ranieri & Ramos, 2013). Inclusive growth is not the same concept as pro-poor growth, and therefore, achieving inclusive growth goes hand-in-hand with sustainable development. Economic growth itself benefits the top earners in the population, and therefore, the pro-poor concept aims to achieve the "trickle-down" effect. While pro-poor growth focuses on people below the poverty line, inclusive growth aims for all economic classes—the poor, near-poor, middle, and high-income earners—to benefit from growth, and also aims to reduce the problems of the most disadvantaged (Saher et al., 2024). Therefore, inclusive growth benefits groups that are otherwise disadvantaged, and as Klasen (2017) referred to it, it is "disadvantaged-reducing growth." In this regard, it is inclusive growth if it reduces regional, ethnic, or gender disadvantages, and this is the main differentiating element of an outcome-focus of inclusive growth from pro-poor growth (Klasen, 2017).

The end of the USSR led to the establishment of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), which excludes the Baltic countries. Grouping the CIS based on state resources and budget revenue sources, three groups can be identified: the first group includes countries exporting energy carriers—Russia, Kazakhstan, and Azerbaijan—whose budgets are filled through hydrocarbon exports; the second group consists of countries exporting labor—Armenia, Moldova, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan—whose budgets are mostly funded through the flow of funds from migrant workers; the third group includes countries with export diversification, such as Belarus, Uzbekistan, and Ukraine, where

along with commodity exports, there is a large proportion of highly processed products (Nosov et al., 2020).

A further comparison of the different economies of post-Soviet countries, particularly the CIS, reveals that all went through periods of differing transitions into fiscal policies, which is a more effective tool in tightening the expansionary effect of the economy (Balıkcıoğlu, 2016). The period of political instability, a prevailing budget deficit as a result of reduced economic activities or disconnection from the global economic system, as well as a lack of proper institutions and policies, impacted the ability to achieve sustained GDP growth. These countries passed through periods of recession; however, the resource-rich countries, which include Russia and Azerbaijan, with fiscal potential from their prominent oil reserves, were capable of enjoying periods of economic booms that coincided with increasing oil prices and therefore translated to direct economic growth. The reverse is also true for both countries, as they became oil-dependent; therefore, during periods of decreased oil prices, these countries went through recession and a decrease in economic activities, prolonging the transition period.

It should be noted that both countries have experienced almost similar economic turbulence, and their positions always change with respect to each other. Therefore, a possible solution to this situation is grouping in reference periods, which would help to establish the amount of change in the relationship between countries (Nosov et al., 2020). In addition to common resource bases and other economic indicators, the relevant time-series data are often non-stationary, meaning their statistical properties change over time. This non-stationarity necessitates the use of cointegration techniques in econometric analysis. Economic variables such as consumption expenditure, income, and wealth, which are key indicators of inclusive economic growth, are typically transformed before being used in regression models (Holden & Perman, 1994).

Despite the extensive literature on economic transformation in post-Soviet states and the impact of several internal and external factors in shaping the economic growth trend, especially for Azerbaijan and Russia, there are very limited cointegrated studies. Moreover, there is a growing discourse on inclusive growth, moving from an emphasis on only economic growth to ensuring equitability in addressing problems of poverty, the environment, and sustainable development. However, there are very limited studies exploring the cointegration of inclusive growth indicators between Russia and Azerbaijan. Therefore, this research article seeks to fill that gap by adopting a rigorous econometric approach to add to the growing literature on the cointegration approach to understanding economic growth between countries with shared economic parameters.

Findings:

The statistical analyses were conducted using econometric methods suitable for time-series and panel data. The study first applied unit root tests (Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP)) to check the stationarity of the variables, including GDP per capita, poverty rate, Human Development Index

(HDI), and Gini coefficient, for both Russia and Azerbaijan. Since the data demonstrated non-stationary behavior at levels, the variables were differenced to achieve stationarity.

Subsequently, Johansen cointegration tests were employed to examine the existence of long-run equilibrium relationships among the inclusive economic growth parameters between the two countries. Once cointegration was confirmed, a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was estimated to capture both short-term dynamics and long-term adjustments in the relationship.

Diagnostic tests, including serial correlation LM tests, heteroskedasticity tests, and stability tests (CUSUM and CUSUMSQ), were applied to ensure the robustness and validity of the model. Additionally, Granger causality tests were performed to determine the direction of causality between economic growth and inequality-related indicators.

In addition to econometric modeling, a comparative analysis was conducted to highlight the structural differences and similarities between Russia and Azerbaijan with respect to inclusive economic growth parameters. The analysis focused on GDP per capita, income inequality, poverty rates, and multidimensional measures such as the Human Development Index (HDI).

The results indicate that both countries experienced rapid growth during periods of high oil prices, underscoring the dependency of their economies on natural resource revenues. However, Azerbaijan demonstrated higher growth volatility, with its GDP per capita showing sharp fluctuations, whereas Russia's larger and more diversified economy provided relative stability despite external shocks.

With regard to inequality, the Gini coefficient suggests that Russia has maintained persistently higher income inequality compared to Azerbaijan. This reflects differences in institutional frameworks and the extent of oligarchic influence in Russia's economy versus Azerbaijan's state-led management of oil revenues through the State Oil Fund.

Moreover, while both countries show improvements in HDI scores over the period 2010–2020, Azerbaijan exhibited more substantial gains in education and life expectancy, partly due to targeted social policies funded by oil revenues. Russia, on the other hand, recorded relatively slower progress in non-income dimensions of inclusive growth, largely constrained by external sanctions and structural inefficiencies.

This comparative assessment complements the statistical results by contextualizing the econometric findings within broader socioeconomic and institutional dynamics. It underscores the partial convergence of Russia and Azerbaijan in terms of economic growth, but also highlights diverging patterns in inequality reduction and human development outcomes.

Results and Discussion

The results of the econometric analysis reveal the existence of a long-run cointegration relationship between the inclusive economic growth parameters of Russia and Azerbaijan over the period 2010–2020. The Johansen cointegration test confirmed that GDP per

capita, poverty rate, HDI, and the Gini coefficient share a stable long-term equilibrium relationship in both economies. This indicates that despite short-term fluctuations, the two countries demonstrate a tendency to converge in terms of growth and inclusivity indicators.

The **Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)** results suggest that deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at a moderate speed, with Azerbaijan showing faster adjustment compared to Russia. This finding reflects Azerbaijan's stronger reliance on oil revenues and state-led stabilization policies, particularly through the State Oil Fund, which has provided fiscal buffers during periods of global economic downturn. Russia, on the other hand, exhibited slower adjustment due to its larger economic size, institutional inefficiencies, and exposure to external sanctions and geopolitical shocks.

The **Granger causality tests** further demonstrated a bidirectional causal relationship between GDP per capita and poverty reduction in Azerbaijan, while in Russia the causality was predominantly unidirectional, from GDP growth to inequality reduction. This indicates that Azerbaijan's social policies and redistributive mechanisms have been relatively more effective in translating economic growth into inclusive development outcomes.

The comparative analysis highlights that while both countries benefited from resource-driven growth, Azerbaijan achieved more significant progress in HDI components, particularly education and life expectancy, whereas Russia struggled with persistent inequality and structural rigidities. These results align with the existing literature on resource-dependent economies but also suggest that institutional frameworks and policy design play a critical role in shaping inclusive outcomes.

Overall, the findings support the argument that resource-based growth can foster inclusive development when accompanied by effective policy mechanisms. However, the differences between Russia and Azerbaijan underscore the importance of institutional quality, governance, and external economic pressures in determining the extent of convergence in inclusive growth parameters.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of this study, several policy suggestions can be made to strengthen inclusive economic growth in both Russia and Azerbaijan:

1. **Diversification beyond oil and gas** – Both economies remain highly dependent on hydrocarbons. Diversification into non-oil sectors such as manufacturing, agriculture, and services is essential for reducing vulnerability to external shocks and ensuring sustainable growth.

2. **Strengthening institutional frameworks** – Russia should address structural inefficiencies and reduce oligarchic dominance, while Azerbaijan should continue to reinforce the transparency and accountability of the State Oil Fund. Effective governance mechanisms are critical for translating growth into equitable outcomes.

3. **Enhancing social policies** – Azerbaijan has demonstrated that targeted social spending can reduce

inequality and improve HDI outcomes. Russia could adopt similar redistributive mechanisms, with a focus on education, healthcare, and social protection for disadvantaged groups.

4. Promoting regional cooperation – Both countries can benefit from closer economic cooperation within the post-Soviet space by sharing best practices in fiscal management, institutional reforms, and inclusive development strategies.

5. Adapting to global challenges – Future strategies should incorporate climate change adaptation, digital transformation, and green energy investments to ensure long-term resilience and inclusivity.

By implementing these recommendations, Russia and Azerbaijan can strengthen the inclusivity of their growth trajectories and provide a framework for other resource-dependent economies in the post-Soviet region.

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